

Holy City in Matthew 4:5 and 27:53

Yung Suk Kim

*Samuel DeWitt Proctor School of Theology
Virginia Union University*

ABSTRACT

This article reevaluates the phrase “the holy city” in the Gospel of Matthew (4:5 and 27:53), challenging the common scholarly interpretation that views the term as purely ironic. Contrasting Matthew’s depiction with the apocalyptic cities of Revelation and Second Temple literature, the study argues that the Gospel presents “the holy city” as a practical, political alternative to corrupt, Roman-affiliated Jerusalem. By analyzing its placement during Jesus’ temptation and the saints’ resurrection, the author contends that Matthew uses the phrase to critique imperial power and affirm a realized vision of justice for his community.

Keywords: Gospel of Matthew, holy city, apocalyptic tradition, theology

INTRODUCTION

New Testament scholarship has not made significant efforts to explore the distinctive use of “the holy city” in Matthew, though some scholars note its ironic usage given the Gospel’s negative portrayal of Jerusalem.¹ Matthew uses the phrase “the holy city” on two occasions (4:5 and 27:53). For the Gospel of Matthew, this city is not an apocalyptic, otherworldly creation (as in Revelation, 11QTemple, and various Pseudepigrapha); rather,

¹ This paper was originally presented at the *Southeastern Region of SBL Annual Meeting*, March 2003, and has since been revised. In general, “the holy city” is none other than Jerusalem (Neh. 11:1, 18; Isa. 48:2; 52:1; Dan. 9:24; Tobit 13:9). Therefore, New Testament scholarship did not care much about it. There are two kinds of interpreters dealing with “the holy city” in Matthew. One group completely ignores the distinctive use of the holy city while equating it with Jerusalem: See David Hill, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1981), 101, 356; Craig S. Keener, *Matthew* (Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 1997); and Donald Senior, *Matthew* (Nashville: Abingdon, 1998), 58. The other group notices its distinctive use but does not explore its significance: For example, Warren Carter observes that “the description of the holy city is ironic in recalling Jerusalem’s calling to serve God yet Jerusalem’s resistance to God’s action in 2:3, 4–6.” See Warren Carter, *Matthew and the Margins* (New York: Orbis Books, 2000), 109, and W. D. Davies and Dale C. Allison, Jr., *The Gospel According to Saint Matthew*, International Critical Commentary, Vol. 3 (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1988), 635. Daniel Patte also observed an ironic use of the holy city; see Daniel Patte, *The Gospel According to Matthew* (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1987), 54–55. Daniel J. Harrington considers that Jerusalem is named the holy city because of the temple of God’s dwelling; see Daniel J. Harrington, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Minnesota: Liturgical Press, 1991), 66.

Correspondence should be addressed to Yung Suk Kim at ykim@vuu.edu.

©2025 Yung Suk Kim. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction, provided the original author and source are credited.

it is a practical and political alternative to the present corrupt, Roman-affiliated Jerusalem, as well as to any imperial city (*polis*). Consequently, Matthew's first use of "holy city" concerns not only the devil's test of Jesus but also the community's challenge to resist the power of the temple-state. The second use of the expression, regarding the appearance of the resurrected saints, suggests that the community's vision of justice is already being realized. Matthew artfully situates "the holy city" in two important narrative moments: the devil's challenge to Jesus in the wilderness test (4:1–11) and the saints' resurrection (27:51–53), which brings hope to Matthew's community.² W. D. Davies rightly observes: "The dead are revived by his dying. As he passes from life to death, they pass from death to life."³

THE HOLY CITY TRADITION

The "holy city" tradition can be traced back to Deutero-Isaiah/Second Isaiah (40–55), who emphasizes "the holiness of God and his vision of God as the great king."⁴ In Isaiah 52 and 53, the holy city holds a connotation that extends beyond the geographical location of Jerusalem. It represents God's people, Israel, while simultaneously depicting God's city as a place where liberated people live in peace, justice, and righteousness. Isaiah 52:1–2 specifically addresses Jerusalem, the holy city, calling for it to be awakened and redeemed by God.

Furthermore, the holy city is conceived as a new mode of resistance to imperialism, a concept drawn from the Septuagint (LXX) reading of Isaiah 66:20. Notably, the LXX version prefers "city" (*polis*) to "mountain," reading "the holy city Jerusalem" instead of "the holy mountain Jerusalem." This lexical change is not accidental, as a mountain is distinct from a city. This shift should be understood within the framework of the LXX as a whole, where city-related words (*polis*) occur 907 times, compared to only 555 occurrences in the Hebrew Bible. This increased prevalence of city usage in the LXX implies that the social, political, economic, and religious contexts of the text are deeply rooted in urban culture. Matthew uses "city" 27 times, suggesting that his community also resides in an urban setting.

The most reasonable conclusion for this emphasis on the city is found in the social history of the time. The LXX translation began around the third century B.C.E., a period characterized by the spread of Greco-Roman imperialism throughout the Mediterranean world.⁵ Therefore, one can infer that the translators of the LXX intended to counteract the influence of imperial cities by asserting Jerusalem as the holy city in Isaiah 66:20. In this verse, the message is unmistakable: All nations are to come to the holy city, Jerusalem, with offerings. This message can be interpreted as a form of political and religious resistance to Greco-Roman imperialism.

² W. D. Davies and Dale C. Allison, Jr., *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on The Gospel According to Saint Matthew*, Vol. 3 (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1988), 633.

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ J. J. M. Roberts, "Introduction to Isaiah," in *The HarperCollins Study Bible*, ed. Wayne A. Meeks (New York: HarperCollins, 1993), 1012–1013.

⁵ Melvin K. H. Peters, "Septuagint," in *Anchor Bible Dictionary*, ed. David Noel Freedman (New York: Doubleday, 1992) vol. 5., 1094.

In the setting of Matthew's post-70 C.E. urban community, this phrasing from the LXX would have resonated deeply, implying that all nations would now come to the holy city through Jesus and his teaching.⁶ At the same time, the community's lived reality required an alternative vision to imperial, urban culture. This vision is embodied in Matthew's use of "the holy city" on two specific occasions, which will be analyzed below.

Even more fascinating is the fact that the phrase in the LXX version of Isaiah 66:20 is identical to Matthew's "holy city" in both instances (4:5 and 27:53). This suggests that Matthew relies on the LXX for his work. The only difference is that Matthew omits the specific name "Jerusalem," an omission intended to highlight the vision of the "holy city" while simultaneously critiquing the corrupt, imperial state of the actual Jerusalem.

Given the community's environment under imperial control, it is first notable this holy city is not an otherworldly realm; rather, the focus is on this world, where the community must live out God's demand for justice and righteousness, echoing the 8th-century B.C.E. prophets Amos and Micah.⁷ Furthermore, Isaiah 52:1 states that "the uncircumcised and the unclean" shall not enter the holy city. In Matthew's context, the "unclean" are the corrupt religious leaders (28:11–15) or those who possess knowledge but fail to act on it (23:13). This explains why it is the resurrected saints who are depicted entering the holy city (27:53), standing in contrast to the unclean leadership.

Second, the holy city tradition is not concerned with a few elect, but with the whole people of God, a vision that extends to the nations as seen in several verses of Isaiah. In Isaiah 42:6, God declares, "I, the Lord, have called you in righteousness." Subsequently, the prophet articulates the necessity of including all nations as the object of salvation: "I will give you as a light to the nations, that my salvation may reach to the end of the earth" (Isaiah 49:6). As such, the holy city tradition does not assert a narrowly defined sectarianism or exclusivism; rather, its vision is practical and embraces all nations.⁸

Third, the holy city tradition serves to promote justice and righteousness through the oracles of judgment on Jerusalem found in Isaiah 3:1–26. Isaiah's vision goes beyond the present warning of destruction to promise the ultimate recovery of the people and the city. As Leslie J. Hoppe rightly observes, "The purpose of Isaiah's oracles of judgment against Jerusalem and its social system was not to announce the end of the city. On the contrary, the prophet believed in the city's future."⁹

HOLY CITY IN APOCALYPTIC LITERATURE

Matthew's community in the post-70 C.E. period stands in contrast to the "otherworldly" holy city concept prevalent in apocalypticism, a tradition often characterized

⁶ This vision of all people coming into the holy city is implied with Jesus' commissioning of his disciples (Matt. 28:16–20).

⁷ William P. Brown and John T. Carroll, "The Garden and the Plaza: Biblical Images of The City" in *Interpretation: A Journal of Bible and Theology* 54, 1 (2000): 3–11.

⁸ Isaiah 60:3: "Nations will come to your light, and kings to the brightness of your dawn."

⁹ Leslie J. Hoppe, *The Holy City: Jerusalem in the Theology of the Old Testament* (Minneapolis: Liturgical Press, 2000), 70.

by the belief that God will grant victory only to the few righteous while destroying the wicked. For instance, the sectarian community associated with the Damascus Document believed that the only true remnant—the righteous—were those members who strictly observed the law: “For when they were unfaithful and forsook Him, He hid His face from Israel and His Sanctuary and delivered them up to the sword” (Damascus Document 1:2).¹⁰ Similarly, 1 Enoch depicts its community as the righteous, anticipating the imminent judgment of the wealthy sinners and the vindication of the oppressed righteous through a series of woes (94:6–11; 95:3–6; 96:5–8; 97:1; 99:1–2, 11–16; 100:7–9).¹¹ Likewise, in 2 Baruch, the few who follow the Torah constitute the true community (18:1–2; 48:18–19). These apocalyptic groups maintained the conviction that only a few would be saved. Their ultimate vision was not to establish the holy city here and now but rather to wait for the New Jerusalem, the holy city coming down from heaven (Rev. 21:1–4).

Another characteristic of apocalyptic literature is cosmic dualism, a framework within which the Qumran community flourished. They hoped that God would bring an end to this world and the wicked, inaugurating a new age for the “sons of light” (1QS 3–4; CD 1:5; 5:18; 1QM).¹² Accordingly, the eschatological battle between the sons of light and the sons of darkness is depicted in the War Scroll.¹³ As a corollary, this apocalyptic worldview tends toward an otherworldly orientation. Consequently, the Qumran community believed that the earthly Jerusalem temple would one day be replaced by a divine one.¹⁴

JERUSALEM IN MATTHEW

Jerusalem is depicted negatively throughout Matthew’s narrative, a deliberate design intended to contrast the actual city with the vision of “the holy city.” As a center of power, Jerusalem is the source of Jesus’ opponents; the Pharisees and scribes come from there (15:1), and the chief priests and elders conspire there to cover up Jesus’ resurrection (28:11). King Herod and the religious leadership operate within Jerusalem, devoid of God’s justice and righteousness, as lamented in 23:37: “Jerusalem, Jerusalem, the city that kills the prophets and stones those who are sent to it!” The repetition of the name here highlights its tragic transformation. It has become the opposite of the holy city. Furthermore, Jesus repeatedly predicts Jerusalem as the site of his suffering and death (16:21; 20:17, 18; 21:1, 10; 23:37). By drawing these contrasts, Matthew’s community distinguishes between the physical

¹⁰ Trans. Géza Vermes, *The Complete Dead Sea Scrolls in English* (London: Penguin Books, 2004), 129.

¹¹ Leslie J. Hoppe, *The Holy City: Jerusalem in the Theology of the Old Testament* (Minneapolis: Liturgical Press, 2000), 10.

¹² John J. Collins, “Apocalypses and Apocalypticism” in *Anchor Bible Dictionary*, ed. David Noel Freedman (New York: Doubleday, 1992), vol. 1, 286. See also Andrew J. Overman, *Matthew’s Gospel and Formative Judaism: The Social World of the Matthean Community* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1990), 31. See also James Charlesworth, *The Old and New Testaments* (Harrisburg: Trinity International, 1993), 97.

¹³ John J. Collins, “Apocalypses and Apocalypticism,” 286.

¹⁴ Andrew J. Overman, *Matthew’s Gospel and Formative Judaism*, 7. Likewise, the theme of the heavenly journey is found in Philo’s writings. See Charlesworth, *The Old and New Testaments*, 267. Also, in 2 Baruch 4:2–7, the heavenly Jerusalem motif is found. Similarly, the new Jerusalem, the holy city, comes down from heaven (Rev. 21:2). In Qumran documents 11Q Temple 29.2–10, the temple is replaced by the divine one, which shows the otherworldly emphasis of the community. Jerusalem is the heaven above to which the just ascend (2 Bar 4:1–7).

Jerusalem and the true holy city; for them, Jerusalem represents a corrupt religious, political, and imperial metropolis.

HOLY CITY IN MATTHEW

The Test Scene (4:1–11)

Here, the devil issues a challenge within the holy city (4:5). When the community hears that the devil led Jesus to the “holy city” to test him on the pinnacle of the temple, they understand this as a test not only of Jesus but also of the community itself. The members are effectively placed in Jesus’ position; they, too, are at risk of falling. They feel a tremor of crisis. The very “holiness” of God and the faith of their ancestors are at stake because the devil has taken Jesus there to bring about his downfall within the holy city.

The community has in mind Isaiah 66:20 and 52:1, where the holy city is so sacred that the unclean and uncircumcised are forbidden to enter. Isaiah 66:20 especially emphasizes “the holy city” as God’s city, the destination where all people come with offerings. Thus, in the community’s imagination, it is the community itself standing on the highest point of the temple. The crisis lies in the fact that the holy city—God’s domain of justice, righteousness, and his dwelling place—lies in ruins. This city, representing God’s presence and protection, has been trampled. It is not just the physical city of Jerusalem that is lost, but the very vision and hope of living with justice and peace seems to be collapsing. They are, in a sense, caught between God and the Empire, between life and death.

Because of the devil’s challenge, the community is called to live like Jesus, who confronts and defeats the devil’s power through obedience to God rather than to religious leaders or Roman authority. Chapter 27 confirms Jesus’ obedience to God, even to the point of death. Matthew’s community views the holy city through a double lens: They see it through the tradition of the holy city, but also through the emphatic use of “holy” in opposition to the “imperial” or “unholy” city.

In the wilderness test, the devil assumes the role of an anti-God figure—personifying the imperial city, the emperor, client kings, or local leaders who cooperate with imperial ideology. In fact, this form of imperial power recurs throughout the narrative until the final resurrection: Herod’s attempt to kill the infant Jesus (2:1–12); the religious leaders’ cooperation with Pilate during Jesus’ trial and crucifixion (27); the soldiers’ mocking of Jesus (27:27–31); and the central accusation against Jesus as the “King of Israel” (27:32–44). The imperial system (the imperial city) demands that the community set God aside by treating relative things—such as food, security, and fame—as absolute. The devil’s logic operates as follows: “If you are the Son of God, do as I command: Solve your hunger, jump from the heights, and worship me.” The devil tempts Jesus and the community with the conditional clause: “If you are the Son of God.” The subtle challenge here is the suggestion that the title—Son of God—is more important than the work of the title, which requires the Son to be obedient to God. In the imperial city, having a title or status guarantees honor. Thus, imperial ideology prioritizes title, position, honor, and power, maintaining an oppressive system at the price of justice and righteousness.

In the devil’s testing of Jesus, the community is identified with Jesus. The community is called to live out the “holy city” vision by confronting the massive imperial power of non-holiness: a power demonstrated by Herod’s slaughter of innocent children, the execution of

John the Baptist, and the killing of Jesus. The holy city vision is, therefore, nothing less than a spirit of resistance against the immense imperial power that suppresses righteous people like this community.¹⁵

Turning to the content of the test, three dimensions of life stand out: the economic, the social, and the religious. The first test concerns “food,” a necessity for the community. However, the crucial point is how one obtains food. Jesus could perform miracles, but he refused to do so precisely because the demand came from the devil. The devil intends to tempt Jesus to seek an easy solution to daily economic problems. It should be noted that this test takes place in the wilderness, echoing the Exodus story (Exod. 16), where there was no food or drink. Like the Israelites, the community faces harsh daily realities. The key to this test is the question: Who provides the food and drink?

The temptation suggests that if the community wants an easy solution, it should accept the imperial system, in which food is supplied through unnatural means. Making bread out of stones is unnatural because stones are intended for building, as Jesus later states (21:42). In contrast, when feeding the five thousand, Jesus did not make bread from stone but multiplied existing food—five loaves and two fish (14:17). Through this first test, the community is reminded that it is God who provides, not the imperial system that perverts the natural order.

The second test concerns the security of the community. Traditionally, security is guaranteed by God in the temple, as it is the symbol of God’s presence. The devil taking Jesus to the pinnacle of the temple in the holy city is strikingly unnatural; while the inner temple is a place of God’s presence and security, the devil’s temptation is to entice Jesus to jump away from the temple—symbolically moving outside of God’s presence. The devil’s proposition to the community might be phrased, “Can you be safe from this height if you jump? Yes! God will protect you.” This is a genuine temptation for a community that lacks protection and security in society. The promise of security and fame offered by the dominant culture is the challenge and test.

The third test of the community concerns the religious dimension, calling into question the community’s ultimate obedience: Whom will you worship—God or Baal? God or the Empire? The high mountain where the devil took Jesus is reminiscent of the mountains in the Old Testament where high places are sites of God’s revelation (Mt. Sinai, Exod. 19) and sites of testing, such as Elijah confronting the prophets of Baal (Mt. Carmel, 1 Kings 18:20–40). On both mountains, God is revealed as the God of Israel who makes a covenant and remains involved through prophets like Moses and Elijah. Through the community’s association with these Old Testament mountain narratives, Matthew’s community identifies itself with the people of Israel as a covenant community. Consequently, they are called to live like Moses, the Israelites, and Elijah, who firmly vowed their obedience to God. This echoes the ultimate choice posed by Moses at the renewal of the covenant: Choose life, not death (Deut. 30:15–20).

Within the Gospel of Matthew itself, the high mountain appears again at the Transfiguration (17:1–13). Here, God reaffirms Jesus on a high mountain: “This is my beloved Son... listen to him” (17:5). Through this heavenly voice, Jesus stands firm in his calling to obey God the Father. Notably, Moses and Elijah appear to speak with Jesus. As mentioned previously, these two Old Testament figures are “mountain people” who assumed leadership roles in calling the Israelites to live in obedience to God. Through all

¹⁵ Warren Carter, *Matthew and Empire: Initial Explorations* (Harrisburg: Trinity International, 2001), 80–81.

these mountain narratives, the ultimate demand placed on the community is clear: They must take a firm stand with God, not with other forms of power, such as imperial authority or corrupt religious leadership. Matthew concludes this section with a verse reminiscent of the Shema, emphasizing the community's exclusive obedience to God: "You shall worship the Lord your God and him only shall you serve" (4:10).

Crucifixion scene (21:51–53)

The tension, threat, and risk of faith created by the devil's challenge to "the holy city" and the community (4:1–11) are partially resolved later in the narrative at 27:51–53. The climactic event of this resolution is the saints' entrance into the holy city. The specific connections between Matthew 4:1–11 and 27:51–53 are outlined in Table 1 below.¹⁶

¹⁶ The idea that Matthew 4:1–11 is contrasted with Matthew 27:51–53 comes from Amy-Jill Levine.

[Table 1]

Item	Test scene (4:1–11)	Crucifixion scene (27:51–53)
Characters	Devil, Jesus	(Jesus), Saints
Item	Test scene (4:1–11)	Crucifixion scene (27:51–53)
Setting	Location: wilderness, the holy city, temple, high mountain Time: temporal	Location: Golgotha, temple, tombs Time: atemporal
Scriptural image	Wilderness: God provides (Exodus 16:1–17:6) Mountain: Elijah's test at Carmel (1 Kings 18:1–46) Moses at Sinai: Forty days and nights (Exodus 24:18; 34:28) (Elijah also: 1 Kings 19:8)	Ezekiel's valley of dry bones: graves opened and bones come back to life (Ezekiel 37:1–14)
Holy city	Devil's entering (threat)	Saints' entering (hope)
Jesus	Tested	Crucified and (resurrected)
Nature	Natural (economic, social, religious dimension)	Supernatural (earthquake, rocks split, curtain rendered, tombs open, saints raised, enter the holy city)
Substance	Stone/bread Holy city/temple High mountain	Rocks split Temple curtain rendered Earthquake (earth shaky)

First, regarding the characters in the wilderness test, the devil took the initiative, and Jesus responded. In contrast, during the crucifixion scene, Jesus is silent while the saints suddenly take center stage as they are raised and enter the holy city. This shift in characters reveals significant points. First, the devil is defeated, and the saints are raised as a direct result of Jesus' death. This event serves as a sign of hope for the community, as the saints can be identified with the community members themselves. These saints evoke the imagery of the dry bones whose lives were renewed in Ezekiel 37:1–14.

The second point concerns ultimate obedience. Jesus passed the initial test in the wilderness, but, in Matthew 27:51–53, he is narrative-wise absent, because he has died on

the cross. This suggests that passing the initial test was not the end; rather, the true test concerns death,¹⁷ demonstrating Jesus' ultimate obedience to God.¹⁸ The implication for the community is clear: A one-time victory is not enough; what truly matters is trusting God to the point of death. Jesus fundamentally demonstrates to the community what true faith and obedience look like. Jesus died amidst the loud cry, the earthquake, and the splitting of rocks, but that is not the end. With the opening of the tombs, the saints are raised and enter the holy city. This presents sheer irony and contrast: One dies, but many are raised. This image alludes to a dawning morning, following a stormy night. At this point in chapter 27, the community reemerges through the saints' entry into the holy city.

Regarding the setting, the test scene primarily addresses the present time, reflecting the lived reality of the community through Old Testament imagery (the wilderness, the holy city, the temple, the high mountain (see Table 1)). The challenge for the community is how to navigate this wilderness-like life—how to maintain the vision of the holy city without bowing down to idols or dominant powers (economic, political, or religious) and deciding whom to serve. In contrast, the crucifixion scene (27:51–53) deals with atemporal, supernatural signs, culminating in the resurrection of the saints. God destabilizes earthly foundations with earthquakes, split rocks, and torn curtains. Thus, for the community, these supernatural signs are more than just a manifestation of God's power; they serve as a reminder that all material foundations are shaky.

Regarding the scriptural imagery, the test scene is rich with biblical references. Here, the community is reminded that only God provides for people in the wilderness. Much like Elijah, the community faces Baal-like idols in various forms. In the crucifixion scene, the community hears the good news of the saints' resurrection. This news vividly echoes Ezekiel's vision, where the dry bones of Israel are brought back to life—a vision that gave hope to a people in exile. Likewise, this community finds hope in God's assurance while living under an exile-like imperial system. Their hope lies in overcoming such oppressive powers.

Now, let us focus on the holy city as a result of Jesus' death. In Matthew 27:53, the "holy" people (the saints) stand in parallel with the "holy" city. This suggests that holy people belong within the holy city, a concept reminiscent of the Old Testament tradition where the holy city is equated with God's people, Israel (Isaiah 48:2). It is God's city, where God's people dwell. Thus, the pairing of "holy" people and the "holy city" strongly implies that this tradition is being reaffirmed in the narrative. Amy-Jill Levine similarly observes that these holy people appear here as an image of continuity linking the past, present, and future.¹⁹ Furthermore, it is crucial to note that these holy people did not enter a heavenly

¹⁷ Daniel J. Harrington, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Minnesota: Liturgical Press, 1991), 401. Harrington says, "Matthew wanted to show that Jesus' death marks a turning point in human history because it makes possible the resurrection of other human beings." But, Harrington misses the fact that Jesus' death also has to do with Matthew's community and, thus, the present reality of Jesus' death and resurrection. The traditional exegesis of verse 27:53–54 has been done centering on an apocalyptic sense. For example, Harrington suggests that the resurrection of the saints and Jesus' resurrection foretell "the fullness that accompanies the end-time" (400–401). But, my contention is that the resurrection and the holy city have to do with recovery of the holy city vision.

¹⁸ Ulrich Luz, *Matthew 1–7: A Continental Commentary*, trans. Wilhelm Linss (Minneapolis: Fortress, 1992), 185.

¹⁹ Amy-Jill Levine, *The Social and Ethnic Dimensions of Matthean Social History* (New York: E. Mellen Press, 1988), 70.

Jerusalem or an otherworldly city; rather, they entered the earthly holy city in the narrative's "here and now" to testify about Jesus to many people. This fact reflects the setting of Matthew's community, whose members must contend for the "holy city" vision in their daily lives.

CONCLUSION

Due to the overwhelming focus on the Christological significance of Jesus' death and resurrection, the important aspects of the "holy city" and the "holy people" in relation to the community's situation have been largely disregarded. Consequently, the phrase "after his resurrection" (27:53) has typically been understood merely to support the priority of Jesus' resurrection. This logic stems from an apocalyptic interpretation in which all events race toward a final consummation.²⁰ However, the point is not who is raised first; rather, it is about the community's identification with the holy people who struggled and suffered like Jesus, and who, like him, went down to the tomb. In other words, the holy people demonstrate solidarity with Jesus by waiting for him until his resurrection.

The holy city vision is a vital reality for Matthew's community as it struggles in the face of imperial theology. I also propose that the Matthean vision for the holy city is not confined to Jerusalem but extends to the whole people of God. This vision is not a new creation of the community; rather, it is derived from the holy city tradition of the Old Testament. Therefore, the Gospel of Matthew is the story of a community struggling for life on the edge of a huge imperial power that suppresses them.

²⁰ Daniel J. Harrington, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Minnesota: Liturgical Press, 1991), 400–401.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Brown, William P., and John T. Carroll. "The Garden and the Plaza: Biblical Images of The City." *Interpretation: A Journal of Bible and Theology* 54, no. 1 (2000): 3-11.

Carter, Warren. *Matthew and Empire: Initial Explorations*. Harrisburg, PA: Trinity International Press, 2001.

———. *Matthew and the Margins*. Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 2000.

Charlesworth, James. *The Old and New Testaments*. Harrisburg, PA: Trinity Press International, 1993.

Collins, John J. "Apocalypses and Apocalypticism." In *Anchor Bible Dictionary*. Edited by David Noel Freedman, 1:286. New York: Doubleday, 1992.

Davies, W.D, and Dale C. Allison, Jr. *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on The Gospel According to Saint Matthew*. Vols. 1 and 3. Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1988.

Harrington, Daniel J. *The Gospel of Matthew*. Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 1991.

Hill, David. *The Gospel of Matthew*. Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1981.

Hoppe, Leslie J. *The Holy City: Jerusalem in the Theology of the Old Testament*. Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 2000.

Keener, Craig S. *Matthew*. Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 1997.

Levine, Amy-Jill. *The Social and Ethnic Dimensions of Matthean Social History*. New York: Edwin Mellen Press, 1988.

Luz, Ulrich. *Matthew 1-7: A Continental Commentary*. Translated by Wilhelm C. Linss. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1992.

Overman, Andrew J. *Matthew's Gospel and Formative Judaism: The Social World of the Matthean Community*. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1990.

Patte, Daniel. *The Gospel According to Matthew*. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1987.

Peters, Melvin K. H. "Septuagint." In *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*. Edited by David Noel Freedman, 5:1094. New York: Doubleday, 1992.

Roberts, J. J. M. "Introduction to Isaiah." In *The HarperCollins Study Bible*. Edited by Wayne A. Meeks. New York: HarperCollins, 1993.

Senior, Donald. *Matthew*. Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1998.

Vermes, Géza. *The Complete Dead Sea Scrolls in English*. London: Penguin Books, 2004.